

Finding Vedic Elements in Pāṇini's Sandhi Rules: A Comparative Study of Ṛk-Prātiśākhya and Pāṇinian Grammar

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Abstract: The grammatical genius of Pāṇini is often celebrated through the lens of Classical Sanskrit, yet the roots of his *Aṣṭādhyāyī* are deeply embedded in the soil of the Vedic Prātiśākhya tradition. While Pāṇini's work serves as the definitive manual for the Classical Sanskrit, it incorporates nearly 270 sūtras specifically addressed to Chandas (the Vedas). This research article explores the profound influence of the Rk-prātiśākhya (RP) on Pāṇini's formulation of Sandhi rules. By performing a comparative analysis of specific phonetic categories—such as Praśliṣṭa, Kṣaipra and Abhinihita and demonstrates that Pāṇini's rules are not merely abstract algebraic formulations but are grounded in the descriptive phonetic observations of the early Vedic scholars. The paper argues that Pāṇini's genius lies in his ability to generalize the specific, case-by-case observations of the RP into a universal generative system while preserving the unique "Vedic elements" that characterize the sacred Saṃhitā literature.

Keywords: Pāṇini; Rk-Prātiśākhya; Sandhi; Vedic phonology; Comparative grammar.

1. INTRODUCTION

The tradition of Sanskrit grammar represents one of the most refined intellectual achievements of ancient India. At its pinnacle stands *Pāṇini*, whose *Aṣṭādhyāyī*, containing nearly 4000 sūtras, not only systematized the grammatical structure of Sanskrit but also introduced a formal rule-based model of linguistic description unparalleled in the ancient world. His grammar has influenced not only subsequent Sanskrit grammatical literature but also modern linguistic theory. Yet, despite its originality and precision, the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* did not arise in isolation. It is deeply rooted in earlier linguistic traditions, especially those associated with the Vedas and their ancillary sciences.

Among the six ancillary disciplines or *Ṣaṭ Vedāṅgas* namely- *Chandas* or 'Metrics', *Kalpa* 'Science relating to sacrifice,' *Jyotiṣa* or 'Astronomy', *Nirukta* or 'Etymology', *Śikṣā* 'Phonetics' and *Vyākaraṇa* 'Grammar'. The *Śikṣā* literature, which was composed for correct pronunciation of Vedic sounds occupies a central position. Apart from the *Vedāṅgas*, the *Prātiśākhyas*, specialized phonetic manuals constitute a distinct body of literature associated with the various Vedic schools, known as *Pārṣadas* or Caranas. The *Prātiśākhya* literature represents the earliest stage of Indian linguistic analysis, acting as manual-specific treatises for the various branches (*śākhās*) of the Vedas and offer detailed instructions for correct pronunciation, recitation, and phonological combination. Among these, the *Ṛk-prātiśākhya* (RP), attributed to *Śaunaka*, stands as a foundational text for the *Rgvedic* tradition. The primary objective of this literature was the preservation of the *Saṃhitā-pāṭha* (the continuous recitation making sandhi or combination) by detailing the rules of transformation from the *Pada-pāṭha* (the word-by-word analysis without sandhi or combination).

Sandhi or euphonic combination, is a fundamental feature of Sanskrit phonology. It governs phonetic changes at morpheme and word boundaries and plays a crucial role in both spoken and written forms of the language. In the Vedic tradition, *Sandhi* is not merely a mechanical phonetic process but is intimately connect-

ed with metrical structure, semantic clarity, and ritual efficacy. The *Prātiśākhya*s, therefore, treat *Sandhi* with remarkable precision, classifying various types of combinations and assigning specific terminologies to them.

Pāṇini, by contrast, integrates *Sandhi* into a broader grammatical framework that encompasses morphology, syntax, and semantics. His treatment of *Sandhi* is abstract and generative, relying on a small number of highly general rules that operate through substitution, elision, and augmentation. Despite this abstraction, many of *Pāṇini*'s *Sandhi* rules preserve older Vedic phonological principles, often explicitly marked as *chandasi*, i.e., applicable in Vedic contexts.

The present study seeks to examine this continuity between the *Vedic* and *Pāṇinian* traditions by undertaking a comparative analysis of *Sandhi* rules as expounded in the *Ṛk-Prātiśākhya* and the *Aṣṭādhyāyī*. Special attention is given to vowel combinations (ac-sandhi), as these constitute the most prominent and elaborately discussed category in both systems. By analyzing specific *Sandhi* types such as *praśliṣṭa*, *kṣaipra*, *padavrtti*, *udgrāha*, *bhugna*, and *abhinidhāna*, and correlating them with corresponding *Pāṇinian sūtras*, this paper aims to demonstrate how *Pāṇini*'s grammar both preserves and transforms Vedic phonological knowledge.

2. SANDHI IN THE ṚK-PRĀTIŚĀKHYA AND IN PĀṆINIAN GRAMMAR

2.1 *Sandhi* in the *Ṛk-Prātiśākhya*

The *Prātiśākhya*s are primarily concerned with the phonetic and phonological aspects of Vedic recitation. They prescribe the correct articulation of sounds, the rules governing their combination, and the appropriate intonation and accentuation patterns. Among these, the *Ṛk-Prātiśākhya* (RP) devotes a substantial portion of its discussion to *Sandhi*, reflecting the complexity and importance of phonological combination in the oral transmission of the *Rgveda*.

The RP classifies morphophonemic combinations into four broad categories:

- (i) vowel–vowel combinations,
- (ii) vowel–consonant combinations,
- (iii) consonant–vowel combinations, and
- (iv) consonant–consonant combinations.

Within these broad categories, the RP further identifies numerous subtypes of *Sandhi* and assigns specific designations to each. This level of classification is far more detailed than that found in *Pāṇini*'s grammar, reflecting the RP's descriptive and text-oriented approach. The RP is not concerned with generating all possible Sanskrit forms but with accurately recording and explaining the phonological phenomena actually observed in the *Rgvedic Samhitā*.

An important feature of the RP's treatment of *Sandhi* is its reliance on concrete examples drawn directly from the *Rgveda*. Each *Sandhi* type is illustrated with multiple citations, demonstrating its occurrence in actual *Vedic* usage. Moreover, the RP frequently notes exceptions and contextual conditions under which certain combinations occur or fail to occur, thereby providing a nuanced and empirically grounded account of Vedic phonology.

2.2 *Sandhi* in *Pāṇinian Grammar*

Pāṇini's *Aṣṭādhyāyī* represents a fundamentally different approach to grammar. Rather than describing specific texts, it aims to provide a comprehensive and generative system capable of producing all well-formed Sanskrit expressions. In this system, *Sandhi* is integrated into the broader framework of morphological derivation and syntactic combination.

Pāṇini classifies Sandhi primarily depending on the sounds involved:

- (i) *ac-sandhi* (vowel–vowel),
- (ii) *hal-sandhi* (consonant–consonant),
- (iii) *visarga-sandhi*,
- (iv) *svādi-sandhi* (related to nominal inflection), and
- (v) *prakṛtibhāva-sandhi* (no change).

The above mentioned five categories, collectively known as *pañca-sandhi-prakarana* in later *prakriyā* works such as the *Siddhāntakaumudī*, provide a general framework for understanding phonological combination in Sanskrit. Unlike the RP, *Pāṇini* does not assign specific names to individual *Sandhi* types such as *praśliṣṭa* or *kṣaipra*. Instead, he formulates general rules that apply across a wide range of contexts, governed by principles of rule interaction, precedence, and exception.

Despite this abstraction, *Pāṇini*'s grammar preserves numerous features of *Vedic* phonology, especially through *sūtras* marked *chandasi*, which are explicitly restricted to *Vedic* usage. These rules often correspond closely to the *Sandhi* phenomena described in the *Prātiśākhya*s, suggesting a direct continuity between the two traditions.

3. COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF VOWEL COMBINATIONS

3.1 Praśliṣṭa-sandhi vs. Savarṇa-dīrgha, Guṇa, and Vṛddhi

In the *Rk-prātiśākhya*, the term *Praśliṣṭa* refers to vowels that "stick together" so closely that they appear inseparable. This single designation in RP covers three distinct operations in *Pāṇini*'s system.

A. Savarṇa-dīrgha (Homogeneous Long Vowel)

Rk-prātiśākhya 2.15:

samānākṣare sasthāne dīrghamekamubhe svaram

(When a simple vowel is followed by its homogeneous counterpart, both are replaced by a long vowel.)

Aṣṭādhyāyī 6.1.101:

akāḥ savarṇe dīrghaḥ

(If a vowel of the *ak* pratyāhāra is followed by a homogeneous vowel, the long form replaces both. Thus, a + a → ā, i + i → ī, u + u → ū, ṛ + ṛ → ṛī, and so on.)

Example: In the Rigveda, we find *aśva + ajani = aśvājani*. Both *Śaunaka* and *Pāṇini* agree on the operation, but *Pāṇini* uses the *pratyāhāra* 'ak' (a, i, u, ṛ, ḷ) to achieve higher algebraic efficiency.

B. Guṇa-sandhi

Rk-prātiśākhya 2.16-17:

ikarodaya ekaramakāraḥ sodayaḥ (a/ā + i/ī becomes e)

tathā ukārodaya okāram (a/ā + u/ū becomes o)

Aṣṭādhyāyī 6.1.87:

ād guṇaḥ

(When a/ā is followed by an *ac* vowel, Guṇa is the single substitute. a + i/ī → e, a + u/ū → o)

Example: a + indra = endra, indra + ā + ihi → indrehi (RV 1.9.1).

Here, a + i results in e.

vāya + u → vāyo (RV 1.2.1)

Here, *Pāṇini*'s "Guṇa" is a functional category, whereas *Śaunaka* explicitly

names the resulting sound. The "Vedic element" here is the specific observation of the *indra* and *uṣa* combinations frequent in the *Ṛk-saṃhitā*.

C. Vṛddhi-sandhi

Ṛk-prātiśākhya 2.18-19:

pareṣvaikāramojayoḥ

aukāram yugmayoḥ

(If diphthongs follow, they result in 'ai' and 'au'. Thus, a + e/ai → ai, a + o/au

→ au (*vṛddhi*.)

Aṣṭādhyāyī 6.1.88:

vṛddhireci

(When a/ā is followed by the *ec* pratyāhāra, Vṛddhi is the substitute.)

Example: *yatra* + *oṣadhīḥ* → *yatrauṣadhīḥ* (RV 10.97.6).

For these three operations, *Śaunaka* provides six *sūtras*, while *Pāṇini* provides three. This illustrates *Pāṇini*'s drive toward brevity (*lāghava*) without losing the phonetic truth established by his predecessors

3.2 Kṣaipra-sandhi vs. Yaṇ-sandhi

The RP uses the term *Kṣaipra* (from *kṣipra*, meaning 'quick') to describe the phonetic transformation where a vowel is pronounced so rapidly that it turns into a semi-vowel.

Ṛk-prātiśākhya 2.21-23:

samānakṣaramantasthām svāmakaṇṭhyam svarodayam

na samānakṣare sve sve

te kṣaiprāḥ prākṛtodayāḥ

(The above RP *sūtras* states that the vowels *i/ī*, *u/ū*, *r/ṛ*, *l* are replaced by the semivowels *y*, *v*, *r*, *l* respectively when followed by a vowel other than the vowel homogenous to the preceding one.)

Aṣṭādhyāyī 6.1.77:

iko yaṇ aci

(The *ik* {*i*, *u*, *r*, *l*} vowels become *yaṇ* {*y*, *v*, *r*, *l*} semi-vowels when followed by an *ac* vowel.)

Example: *adhi* + *nvatra* → *adhinnvatra* (RV 10.93.15).

This *sūtra* states that the vowels *i*, *ī*, *u*, *ū*, *r*, and *ṛ* are replaced by the semi-vowels *y*, *v*, *r*, and *l* respectively when followed by a vowel. Thus, the RP's *kṣaipra-sandhi* corresponds exactly to *Pāṇini*'s *yaṇ-sandhi*, although the RP primarily emphasizes *i* and *u*, reflecting the most common Vedic occurrences.

3.3 Padavṛtti

In Vedic recitation, it is common for two vowels to remain side-by-side without coalescing. This is called *Padavṛtti* (or *hiatus*). In Classical Sanskrit, hiatus is generally avoided, but *Pāṇini* must account for it to satisfy Vedic requirements.

A. Deletion of 'h' or Visarjanīyaḥ

Ṛk-prātiśākhya 2.24:

Visarjanīyo riphito dīrghapūrvah svarodayaḥ ākāram

Along with the preceding *visarjanīya* not originated from a *repha*, the preceding long velar vowel *āh* will change into *ā* if it is followed by a vowel-short or long. In other words, in the combination *āh* + any vowel (short/long), *āh* final will be replaced by a long *ā*.

Example: *yāḥ oṣadhīḥ* → *yā + oṣadhīḥ* (RV. 10.97.18)

(The *Visarga* (*h*) is dropped here though 'a' and 'o' are side-by-side, they do not become 'au' (*Vṛddhi*.)

When Śaunaka directly transforms *āh* into *ā*, Pāṇini justifies this transformation by a relatively longer formation procedure. This is because of the intricacies of ordering technique of the *sūtras* in view of their strength in terms of *paranīya-antaranga* and *apavāda* nature.

This goes like *yāh + osadhīh > yās + osadhīh* (by P. 8.3.34): *visarjanīyasya sah > yār osadhīh* (by P. 8.2.66 *sa sajusō ruh*) / *yāy + osadhīh* (by P. 8.3.17 *bhobhogoagho-apūrvasya yo śi*) > *yā ośadhīh* by (P. 8.3.19: *lopaḥ śākalyaya*).

No further combination resulting in a common *au* by P. 6.1.88 in place of a + o is possible due to the *asiddhatva* of the preceding *sūtra* P. 8.3.19 which causes the dropping of *y*.

B. Deletion of 'y' or 'v' (from Diphthongs)

R̥k-prāṭiśākhya 2.25-26

uttamau ca dvau svarau

tāḥ padavrttayaḥ

When the diphthongs *ai* or *au* appear at the end of a word followed by a vowel, they technically turn into *āy* and *āv*. The *ai/au* is therefore replaced with *ā*. According to the *Vedic* tradition (and Pāṇini's reference to *Śākalya*), the 'y' or 'v' is dropped, creating a *Padavrtti*.

Example: *tasmai + indrāya* → *tasmā indrāya*

(Here *tasmai* becomes *tasmāy*. But the 'y' is dropped here and there is no further Sandhi between *ā* and *i*.)

Aṣṭādhyāyī 8.3.19:

lopaḥ śākalyasya

(The 'y' is dropped according to Śākalya.)

Example: *yāh + ośadhīh* → *yā ośadhīh*.

Pāṇini's technical genius uses the principle of **Asiddhatva** (invalidity). According to Pāṇini, *yāḥ* becomes *yāy*, and then the *y* is dropped. However, the rule that would normally combine *yā + o* (*Vṛddhi*) cannot "see" that the *y* is gone because the deletion rule is in the *Tripādī* section (the last three chapters of the *Aṣṭādhyāyī*), which are considered non-existent for the earlier rules. This complex technicality is Pāṇini's way of justifying the *Vedic* hiatus (*Padavrtti*) within a rigid rule-based system.

3.4 Abhinihita-sandhi vs. Pūrvarūpa

Abhinihita refers to the "prodelision" or "absorbing" of an initial *a* after a final *e* or *o*.

R̥k-prāṭiśākhya 2.34:

athābhinihitaḥ sandhir etaiḥ prakṛta-vaikṛtaiḥ/ekībhavati pādādirakāraṣṭe'tra sandhijāḥ

Aṣṭādhyāyī 6.1.109:

eṅaḥ padāntādati

(Final *e* or *o* followed by short *a* result in the previous form, known as *pūrvarūpa sandhi* in classical Sanskrit.)

Example: *dāsuṣe + agne* → *dāsuṣe'gne* (RV 1.94.14).

Śaunaka notes that this absorption is mandatory in certain *R̥k* lines but restricted if the *a* is at the start of a *pāda*. Pāṇini incorporates this *Vedic* nuance in:

P. 6.1.115: prakṛtyāntaḥ pādamayapare

(Inside a *pāda*, the hiatus remains unchanged if followed by certain sounds.)

This is a direct "Vedic element" where Pāṇini suspends his general rule for Classical Sanskrit to preserve the specific rhythmic structure of the *R̥gveda*.

3.5 Bhugna-sandhi: The Origin of v-augmentation

In RP, *Bhugna* is the augmentation of v after labial vowels (o, au) when non-labial vowels follow.

Rk-prāṭisākhya 2.31

oṣṭhyayonyorbhugnamanoṣṭhye vakāro 'trāntarāgamaḥ

Example: vāyo + āyāhi vāyavāyāhi (RV 1.2.1).

Pāṇini's *sūtra* 6.1.78 (*eco'yāvāyāvah*) is a brilliant generalization. Instead of naming the *sandhi* "*Bhugna*," Pāṇini creates a simultaneous mapping system (*e* = *ay*, *o* = *av*, *ai* = *āy*, *au* = *āv*). The Vedic "*Bhugna*" is thus revealed as the specific laboratory where the universal rule of Pāṇini was discovered.

4. DISCUSSION: THE INFLUENCE OF ŚĀKALYA AND THE PRE-PĀṆINIAN TRADITION

Pāṇini frequently cites Śākalya, the celebrated author of the *Rigvedic Pada-pāṭha*. In the *Aṣṭādhyāyī*, Śākalya's name is invoked precisely where Pāṇini needs to account for Vedic variations—particularly in rules concerning *Lopa* and *Pragrhya* (uncombinable vowels).

This citation of Śākalya serves as the strongest evidence of the "Vedic elements" in Pāṇinian *Sandhi*. Pāṇini acknowledges that for the Vedic language, the rules of the *Prāṭisākhya*s are authoritative. By incorporating rules such as *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 1.1.11 *īdūded dvi-vacanaṃ pragrhyam*, Pāṇini ensures that his grammar can generate the exact forms found in the *Samhitās*, even when they contradict the standard rules of the Classical *Bhāṣā*.

5. COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT

The foregoing analysis demonstrates a strong continuity between the *Sandhi* rules of the *Rk-Prāṭisākhya* and those of Pāṇini's *Aṣṭādhyāyī*. Nearly every vowel combination type described in the RP finds a precise parallel in Pāṇini's grammar, often through one or more *sūtras*. This continuity suggests that Pāṇini was deeply familiar with the Vedic phonological tradition and consciously incorporated its insights into his grammatical system.

At the same time, significant methodological differences exist between the two traditions. The RP adopts a descriptive, text-bound approach, focusing on actual phonological phenomena observed in the *Rgveda*. It provides numerous examples, detailed classifications, and exhaustive lists of exceptions. Pāṇini, by contrast, adopts an abstract, generative approach, formulating highly general rules that apply across a wide range of contexts. His grammar aims not merely to describe existing texts but to generate all well-formed Sanskrit expressions.

These methodological differences are reflected in the structure and presentation of *Sandhi* rules. The RP assigns specific names to individual *Sandhi* types and treats them separately, whereas Pāṇini subsumes multiple phenomena under a single rule or a small set of rules. For example, the RP distinguishes *praśliṣṭa*, *kṣaipra*, *padavṛtti*, *udgrāha*, *bhugna*, and *abhinidhāna* as separate categories, while Pāṇini accounts for these through a limited number of *sūtras* such as *vṛd-dhireci* (P. 6.1.88), *ādguṇaḥ* (P. 6.1.87), *akaḥ savarṇe dīrghaḥ* (P. 6.1.101), *iko yaṇ aci* (P. 6.1.77), *eco'yāvāyāvah*, (P. 6.1.78), and *enaḥ padāntād ati* (P. 6.1.109).

Despite this abstraction, Pāṇini preserves numerous Vedic-specific features through *chandasi* rules and optional operations. These rules allow for phonological patterns that are characteristic of Vedic Sanskrit but not of later Classical Sanskrit, thereby maintaining continuity with the older tradition while accommodating lin-

guistic change.

6. CONCLUSION

This comparative study between the *Prātiśākhya* and *Pāṇiniyān* work has demonstrated that *Pāṇini's* *Sandhi* rules are deeply rooted in Vedic phonological traditions as preserved in the *Ṛk-Prātiśākhya*. While *Pāṇini's* grammar represents a methodological innovation through its abstract, rule-based system, it does not sever its connection with earlier Vedic linguistic thought. Instead, it refines and systematizes it.

Processes such as *savarṇa-dīrgha*, *guṇa*, *vṛddhi*, *yañ*, *pūrvarūpa*, and *prakṛtibhāva* elaborately described in the RP, reappear in *Pāṇini's* system in a more concise form. Regional and contextual variations preserved in the RP—such as *Prācyā* and *Pañcāla-padavṛtti* and *abhinidhāna* exceptions—are accommodated in *Pāṇini* through *chandasi* rules and optional operations.

This study thus highlights both the continuity of Sanskrit phonology and the evolution of grammatical thought from a descriptive, text-oriented tradition to a formal, generative one. It shows that the importance of the *Prātiśākhyas* not merely as auxiliary texts or text of accentuation but as foundational works that shaped the very structure of *Pāṇinian* grammar.

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